

LEXICOGRAPHIC INTERPRETATION OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH TRANSLATION DICTIONARIES

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Due to the fact that most words in the English language are polysemantic and polyfunctional, the dictionary article contains information about the category of its meaning (this should be noted as the first difference in the interpretation of words in Uzbek). Such a pometa applies equally to all polysemantic and polyfunctional word interpretations. English online dictionaries have a wide range of definitions of words. We exemplify and analyze only comments relevant to our research subject, relying on the concept of category membership.

Explanation of adverbs denoting status in the explanatory dictionary of the English language.

Also, in the explanatory dictionaries of the English language, there are lexemes that express the situation clearly in the word patterns of the verb group.

Feel verb to experience something physically or emotionally:

"How are you feeling?" "Not too bad, but I've still got a slight headache."

How would you feel about moving to a different city?

He's still feeling a little weak after his operation.

My eyes feel really sore.

Feel is a lexeme that represents the human condition, or rather, the level of feeling. In the semantic description of the word, it is given as "physical or emotional feeling of something".

FEEL verb

transitive verb

1a: to handle or touch in order to examine, test, or explore some quality She felt the fabric to see if it was wool.

b: to perceive by a physical sensation coming from discrete end organs (as of the

skin or muscles) He felt a sudden pain in his leg.

2a: to undergo passive experience of continuously feeling the resentment of his competitors

b: to have one's sensibilities markedly affected by feeling the stroke deeply

3: to ascertain by cautious trial – usually used with out feeling out the sentiments of their neighbors on the subject of school improvements

4a: to be aware of by instinct or inference feeling trouble brewing

b: BELIEVE, THINK say what you really feel

5. US slang: to understand (someone): to know how (someone) feels Yeah, I feel you on that. I fall asleep every time I'm in the car as well. – Scott Sugarman
When you buckle your chinstrap up, it's with a purpose, dog! Do you feel me? – Eric Berry

intransitive verb

1a: to receive or be able to receive a tactile sensation: lost the ability to feel in his fingertips

b: to search for something by using the sense of touch: She felt in her purse for her keys.

2a: to be conscious of an inward impression, state of mind, or physical condition: I feel sick.

b: to have a marked sentiment or opinion: feels strongly about it

3: SEEM it feels like spring today

4: to have sympathy or pity: I feel for you

feel like: to have an inclination for: feel like a walk?

This dictionary article reveals the polysemantic feature of the lexeme feel: both the transitive and intransitive forms of this word are the same – state. When it is a transitive verb, to touch to examine, test, or learn the quality of something; feeling with a body part; constantly experiencing the opposition's displeasure; to be strongly affected by one's feelings, to feel insults deeply; comes in senses such as understanding by instinct or inference. As an intransitive verb, perceive the feeling of touch; to look for something using the sense of touch; knowing an inner impression, state of mind, or physical condition; is interpreted as sympathy or compassion. It can be seen from the comment that the meanings of the word feel, described in the dictionary as a polysemantic lexeme, differ from each other with a subtle stylistic/emotional tone.

References:

1. Alimsaidova S. A. Comparison of spatial constructions in the Russian and Uzbek languages in the formation of sociolinguistic competence //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 7. – C. 204-214.
2. Alimsaidova Sayyora Amideevna. "Historical and literary texts as the basis for teaching a non-native language." Current research journal of pedagogics 2.10 (2021): 204-208.
3. Isakova, Shohida. "The Role of Parents in Foreign Language Teaching." The Peerian Journal 4 (2022): 13-16.
4. Mirmuhsin Yuldashev Munavvarjon o'gli. "Development of short story genre in american literature". European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements, vol. 3, no. 6, June 2022, pp. 18-19.
5. Mirmuhsin Yuldashev. Flash fiction as an innovation in lydia davis's short stories. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research (2022): Pp.422-425.
6. Mirmuhsin Yuldashev. Modern tendencies in american short story genre. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. 2021, Volume : 11, Issue : 6. Pp. 918-919.
7. Mukhammadjon Solijonov and Kholiqova Lutfiya. Linguistics in the anthropocentric paradigm methodological foundations of science. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research (2022): 174-177.
8. Mukhammadjon Solijonov. Linguistic and extralinguistic factors forming the conceptual field of parables. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research (2022): Pp. 414-417.
9. Tillahodshajeva, F. (2023). Schiller in Uzbekistan. International scientific conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education", 2(1). Pp. 51-55.
10. Tillyakhodzhaeva F. (2021). Features of the development of mathematical abilities of students in English lessons. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crjp-02-11-41>
11. Tilyakhodzhaeva F.M. Artistic Features in the Stories of Adalbert Stifter. Central Asian journal of social sciences and history 4.1 (2023): 10-13.
12. Tilyakhodzhaeva Fazilya. From the experience of using the clil

methodology in Uzbekistan. Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review (2022): Pp. 249-255.

13. Tilyakhodzhaeva Fazilya. Required English linguistic knowledge for teaching math in English. The American Journal of Applied sciences 5.01 (2023): 1-4.